

Research Article

Design and fabrication of pneumatic ramming machine for sand casting mould

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Abstract: This paper described that molding is one of the important metals forming process in manufacturing components for various applications in industry. Casting of any size and shape can be made accurately. Automation in this field helps to improve the foundry environment and accuracy of the cast parts. Efficiency of molding is affected by various parameters like permeability, collapsibility, adhesiveness etc. So it is a must to avoid defects in casting. The defects occur in sand castings post a great problem in foundry. On account of defects more than 10% castings are rejected. Even though skilled labor is employed for ramming operation, the packing of molding sand will not be even throughout the molding box. So we have selected the idea of fabricating pneumatic rammer. This rammer is operated pneumatically. By using this rammer molding sand will be packed evenly throughout the box.

Keywords: Molding, Casting, permeability, collapsibility, adhesiveness, pneumatically

1. Introduction

A mold or mould is a hollowed-out block that is filled with a liquid or pliable material such as plastic, glass, metal, or ceramic raw material. The liquid hardens or sets inside the mold, adopting its shape. A mold is the counterpart to a cast. Two plate molds is the easiest injection mold structure and has many advantages [1]. It's consist with A side and B side 2 main parts, when it is load in ejection machine to do molding, A side is fixed and held still, B side is

movable. Figure 1 shows the details of the two plate mould with a special cavity and core slide in the molding process which is a good and significant terminology [2].

Figure 1 Two plate mold design

1.1. Standard mould

A side core is a local core which is normally mounted at right angled to the mould axis for forming a hole or recess in the side face of a molding. The side cavity performs a similar function to the side core, in that it permits the molding of components which are not in line of draw [3]. The schematic of standard mould is shown in Figure 2. Similarly some other competent moulds are discussed in theoretical form.

Figure 2 Schematic of standard mould

Molded threads are everywhere on the cap of a soda bottle. On the nut that attaches the drain pipe to the underside of the kitchen sink. On those weird-looking screws used to assemble a

child's jungle gym. These are just a few examples of the mass-produced plastic parts we encounter every day, parts that were made using multi-cavity, highly automated molds costing hundreds of thousands of dollars and requiring many months to design and manufacture. These have two to three plates, which are clutched in the mold base. Using sprue, the plastic is injected into the cold runner mould, going to the parts in the cavity. The parts and the runner system are joined in the two plate moulds. An ejection method is utilized to make the pair from the mould part. Remember when you were just a kid and you were assembling a robot or a car? Surely, you have noticed that parts of your toy were not separated from the runners. It was you who were the one that separated them. On the other hand, in three-plate plastic moulds, only the parts are ejected as the runner is placed on a different plate [4]. Hot runner moulds consist two primary categories: internally and externally heated systems. Externally heated systems are more suitable to polymers because they are susceptible to thermal forms. Internally heated systems, on the other hand, promote a more excellent flow control. These types of plastic moulds are comprised of two plates that are heated using the manifold system, which drives the dissolved plastic to nozzles. These nozzles fill up the part cavities. Unlike in the cold runner moulds, hot runner moulds completely remove runners thus they create no impact in cycle times. The insulated runner is a modification of this system. Instead of heat, the insulation maintains the plastic in its melted condition. It can only accept small numbers of plastics, particularly the semi-crystalline polymers as it carries low thermal conductivity.

1.2. Sand casting

Least expensive in small quantities (less than 100) Ferrous and non - ferrous metals may be cast possible to cast very large parts and bull shape with least expensive tooling. Dimensional accuracy inferior to other processes, requires larger tolerances castings usually exceed calculated weight Surface finish of ferrous castings usually exceeds 125 RMS. Use when strength/weight ratio permits tolerances, surface finish and low machining cost does not warrant a more expensive process. To enable this compatibility a piece of equipment is used in foundry .A conventional sand rammer used to have a calibrated sliding weight actuated cam, which used to be actuated manually on to the required specimen, but this method was not satisfactory when it comes to mass production with large mould. Hence several experimentation have been going on to improve the quality and reduce time used for ramming process, where pneumatically actuated rammer is one type of idea where the rammer is completely actuated with the help of pneumatic

controls and the time used for ramming is also reduced to an effective duration [5]. Figure 4 shows the structure of sand casting and similarly the Figure 4 shows the structure of plastic casting.

Figure 3 Structure of Sand casting

Figure 4 Structure of plastic casting

1.3. Reciprocating compressors

It uses pistons driven by a crankshaft. They can be either stationary or portable, can be single or multi-staged, and can be driven by electric motors or internal combustion engines. Small reciprocating compressors from 5 to 30 horsepower (hp) are commonly seen in automotive applications and are typically for intermittent duty. Larger reciprocating compressors well over 1,000 hp (750 kW) are commonly found in large industrial and petroleum applications. Discharge pressures can range from low pressure to very high pressure (>18000 psi or 180 MPa). In certain applications, such as air compression, multi-stage double-acting compressors are said

to be the most efficient compressors available, and are typically larger, and more costly than comparable rotary units. Another type of reciprocating compressor, usually employed in automotive cabin air conditioning systems, is the swash plate or wobble plate compressor, which uses pistons moved by a swash plate mounted on a shaft. Household, home workshop, and smaller job site compressors are typically reciprocating compressors 1½ hp or less with an attached receiver tank [6]. A linear compressor is a reciprocating compressor with the piston being the rotor of a linear motor. The design of reciprocating compressor is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Design of reciprocating compressor

Rotary screw compressors use two meshed rotating positive-displacement helical screws to force the gas into a smaller space. These are usually used for continuous operation in commercial and industrial applications and may be either stationary or portable. Their application can be from 3 horsepower (2.2 kW) to over 1,200 horsepower (890 kW) and from low pressure to moderately high pressure (>1,200 psi or 8.3 MPa). The classifications of rotary screw compressors vary based on stages, cooling methods, and drive types among others. Rotary screw compressors are commercially produced in Oil Flooded, Water Flooded and Dry type. The efficiency of rotary compressors depends on the air drier and the selection of air drier is always 1.5 times volumetric delivery of the compressor. Designs with a single screw or three screws instead of two exist.

2. Methodology

2.1. Pneumatic systems

A pneumatic system is a system that uses compressed air to transmit and control energy. Pneumatic systems are used in controlling train doors, automatic production lines, mechanical clamps, etc. Figure 6 shows the Automobile production lines in the industry.

Figure 6 Automobile production lines

2.2. Main pneumatic components

Pneumatic components can be divided into two categories:

1. Components that produce and transport compressed air.
2. Components that consume compressed air.

All main pneumatic components can be represented by simple pneumatic symbols. Each symbol shows only the function of the component it represents, but not its structure. Pneumatic symbols can be combined to form pneumatic diagrams. A pneumatic diagram describes the relations between each pneumatic component, that is, the design of the system. The production and transportation of compressed air Examples of components that produce and transport compressed air include compressors and pressure regulating components.

2.3. Compressors used in study

A compressor can compress air to the required pressures. It can convert the mechanical energy from motors and engines into the potential energy in compressed air (Figure 7). A single central compressor can supply various pneumatic components with compressed air, which is transported

through pipes from the cylinder to the pneumatic components. Compressors can be divided into two classes: reciprocators and rotary.

Figure 7 Design of compressor and pressure regulators

Once a minimum suitable operating pressure has been determined for any compressed air application, it is essential to supply the air at a constant pressure, regardless of upstream flow and pressure fluctuations. Thus it is critical to install the proper regulator or pressure-reducing valve in the airline. Air regulators are special valves that reduce supply pressure to the level required for efficient operation of downstream pneumatic equipment. A filter to protect the regulator's internal passages from damage should always be installed upstream from it. There are several types of air regulators. The simplest type uses an unbalanced-poppet-style valve. This design incorporates an adjustment spring, does not have a separate diaphragm chamber, and is non-relieving. Turning the adjustment screw compresses the spring, which forces the diaphragm to move, thus pushing a poppet to uncover an orifice. As pressure rises downstream, it acts on the underside of the diaphragm, balancing against the force of the spring. The poppet throttles the orifice opening to restrict flow – and produce the desired downstream pressure. A spring under the poppet assures that the valve closes completely when no flow exists. This is the least expensive type air regulator. Larger, more expensive regulators, incorporate a separate diaphragm chamber, which has an aspirator tube exposed to the output pressure. Segregating the diaphragm from the main airflow minimizes its abrasive effects and extends the life of the valve. As flow through this

regulator increases, the aspirator tube creates a slightly lower pressure in the diaphragm chamber. The diaphragm deflects downward and opens the orifice without significantly reducing the output pressure. The effect is the same as increasing the adjustment setting. Thus, this style regulator has minimal drop (output pressure decay) as supply pressure varies. Compares how that variance occurs with a small and a large diaphragm. The larger diaphragms in these regulators improve response and sensitivity. As discharge flow through the regulator is increased over its entire range, output pressure drops. Thus it is important to set the regulator's desired output pressure under normal flow conditions.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Directional control valve

Directional control valves are one of the most fundamental parts in hydraulic machinery as well as pneumatic machinery. They allow fluid flow into different paths from one or more sources. They usually consist of a spool inside a cylinder which is mechanically or electrically controlled. The movement of the spool restricts or permits the flow, thus it controls the fluid flow. A 5/2 directional control valve would have five ports and two spool positions. Figure 8 shows the fabricated design of directional control valve.

Figure 8 Fabricated design of directional control valve

3.2. Base frame

It forms the robust supports to stand the machine vertically. It holds the weight of the vertical post and supports the direction control valve. It is made of mild steel. It is made of rectangular base with the vertical post and the horizontal channel. Figure 9 shows the design of base frame.

Figure 9 Design of base frame

An air compressor is a device that converts power (using an electric motor, diesel or gasoline engine, etc.) into potential energy stored in pressurized air (i.e., compressed air). By one of several methods, an air compressor forces more and more air into a storage tank, increasing the pressure. When tank pressure reaches its upper limit the air compressor shuts off. The compressed air, then, is held in the tank until called into use. The energy contained in the compressed air can be used for a variety of applications, utilizing the kinetic energy of the air as it is released and the tank depressurizes. When tank pressure reaches its lower limit, the air compressor turns on again and depressurizes the tank. The Autocad 3D view of the fabricated design is given in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Autocad 3D views

3.3. Design calculations

The force exerted by a double acting pneumatic cylinder can be expressed as below:

$$F=P*A, F=P\pi d^2/4 \text{ Where,}$$

F=force exerted (N)

P=gauge pressure (N/m², P)

A=full bore area (m²)

d=full bore piston diameter (m)

Double acting cylinder-input stroke:

The force exerted by a pneumatic cylinder can be expressed as below:

$$F=p\pi (d1^2-d2^2)/4 \text{ Where,}$$

D1=full bore piston diameter (m)

D2=piston rod diameter (m)

Force calculations:

Pressure of the cylinder=8bar=0.8N/mm²

Diameter of the cylinder=40mm

Diameter of the piston rod=18mm

Calculations-Double acting pistons outstroke:

The force exerted by a single acting pneumatic cylinder with 8bar and full bore diameter of 40mm (0.040m) can be calculated as,

$$F=P (\pi d^2/4)$$

$$F=0.8*1256$$

$$F=1004N$$

Calculation-Double acting piston is stoked:

The force exerted from a single acting pneumatic cylinder with 8bar and full bore diameter of 40mm(0.040m) and rod diameter 18mm(0.018m) can be calculated as,

$$F=P\pi (d1^2-d2^2)/4 = 0.8*3.14(40^2-18^2)/4$$

$$F=801.73N$$

The all results obtained are very precise and suitable for the fabrication process. The designed calculations are accurate and precise throughout designing process.

4. Conclusion

This study proposes that Pneumatic ramming machine is very cheap as compared to hydraulic ramming machine. The range of the ramming sand can be increased by arranging a high pressure compressor and installing more hardened blades. This machine is advantageous to sand ramming process industries as they cannot afford the expensive hydraulic ramming machine, Electromagnetic ramming machine, rack and pinion, and spring ramming machine. Thus our concept complying with the demand of the customer whose use the product as well as those who our new. The latent needs of the customer which they were not able to reciprocate properly is the estimated successfully the individual functions were study and thoroughly and were evaluated further study will involve more analysis about the product and comparison of the similar product available in the market this process has cheaper than other ramming process.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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